

Performance Limitations of an Optical PSK Heterodyne WDM System due to Raman Amplifier Induced Crosstalk

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ABSTRACT

Analysis is carried out for a WDM transmission system with Raman amplifier considering PSK modulation with an optical heterodyne receiver. Analysis includes the effect of crosstalk due to optical Amplifiers Spontaneous Emission (ASE) and receiver noise. The results are evaluated in form of IF signal to noise ratio and bit error rate for different system parameters. It is noticed that the system suffers significant power penalty due to ASE induced crosstalk and penalty is high for higher transmission distance and can be reduced by increasing the local oscillator laser power. Power penalty is found to be 0.9 dB, 1.9 dB, 2.9 dB for a distance of 5 km, 10 km and 15 km respectively for a local oscillator power of 10 mW at a BER of 10^{-10} .

Key words: Phase Shift Keying (PSK); Heterodyne receiver; Raman Amplifier; Fiber Span; Amplifier Spontaneous Emission (ASE)

INTRODUCTION

Raman amplifier is an advanced technology in the field of Internet trafficking and network communication developed by Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) bubble. Although Raman amplifier has been implemented commercially, its performance and Efficiency in practical still needs to be enhanced [1]. In practical implementation there is a lot of barriers which can compensate the advantages of distributed amplification such as crosstalk, ASE (Amplifier Spontaneous Emission) Noise and so on. A lot of work has been done in this field to increase the performance of a WDM system. More precisely the performance of an optical transmission system is largely dependent on optical transmission link. Performance of an optical transmission link is defined by the optical connector, fibre, amplifier, coupler, transmitter and receiver. The performance of an optical amplifier is measured by SCNR (Signal to Crosstalk and Noise Ratio) and BER (Bit Error Rate). The effects of optical amplifiers and optical receiver in the presence of crosstalk on the overall performance, in particular, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Bit-Error-Rate (BER) performance of a DWDM system has been analysed. The system suffers from a power penalty which increases with the decrement in channel spacing and with the increment of optical amplifiers, and number of hops [2] Coherent detection with digital signal processing including quantum noise has been analysed recently. The combination of coherent detection and DSP provides with new capabilities that were not possible without the detection of the phase of the optical signal [3]

Recently Performance of a Raman Amplifier Induced Crosstalk in terms of Bit Error Rate in a WDM Transmission system for Optical On-Off keying (OOK) modulation has been analysed [4]. Considering the ASE noise along with the crosstalk the performance of a WDM system has been evaluated and shown that ASE noise is higher at higher pump power [5]. We have shown that ASE noise power can be reduced if the inter-channel spacing is decreased. To Design a flat gain fibre amplifier suppressing the noise effect a new bidirectional pumping schemes has been found with higher order forward pumping which is better than the conventional pumping [6].

For the same performance, the pulse energy in optical ASK must be twice that in optical PSK. Hence, optical ASK requires 3 dB more power than optical PSK. Thus, in coherent detection, optical PSK is always preferable to optical

ASK. Performance of an optical WDM system in terms of SNR and BER has been analysed for only amplitude shift modulation and found that the BER increases as we move along the fibre [7].

We have analysed an Optical PSK heterodyne WDM system. The performance of a WDM system in case of BPSK and QPSK modulation can be understood from the result. To get constant amplitude as output PSK modulation is used. The power penalty and performance limitations in comparison of OOK modulation is analysed and a suitable modulation is found for a WDM system to travel longer distance with minimum crosstalk and noise.

SYSTEM MODEL

Fig. 1(a) Block Diagram of N Channel WDM System with Raman Amplifier Fibre Span

Fig. 1(b) Block Diagram of Optical Coherent Heterodyne Phase Shift Keying (PSK) Receiver

The block diagram of a WDM system with optical PSK modulation and distributed Raman amplifier is shown in figure 1(a). At first electrical signals were converted into optical signal through a drive circuit. The optical signal is then modulated by a PSK modulator. N data channels are used to modulate N laser source of wavelength λ_1 to λ_N using phase shift keying modulation and are multiplexed by a Wavelength division multiplexer (WDM). An optical heterodyne balanced receiver is shown in figure 1(b) and 1(c). The received signals are demultiplexed by the receiver at the receiving end. In PSK, there are two components of the current. The summand component is passed through a pre-amplifier. A local oscillator power is multiplexed with the signal power in heterodyne system to make it easier detecting the signal. As PSK modulation is used a constant amplitude is received at the receiving end.

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

A WDM system with equally spaced channels is applied on a SMF Raman amplification System. Let us consider that all the channels lie within the linear portion of the Raman gain profile and are equally separated in spectral domain. We evaluate a simplified equation of output current for the system to find out Bit Error Rate (BER) performance. The WDM signal with N number of Channel with PSK modulation is [7]

$$S_{WDM} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^N \sqrt{2P_{s,n}(0)} a_k^n \cos \left[\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_n} t \right] \tag{1}$$

where a_k is the k-th bit of the n-th channel.

The signal from the pump source is

$$S_{pump} = \sqrt{2P_0(0)} \cos \left[\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_p} t \right] \tag{2}$$

Electric field of the WDM system at a distance z is found to

$$e_{WDM}(t, z) = \sum_{n=1}^N e_{s,n}(t, z) + e_{ct,n}(t, z) \quad (3)$$

where electric field due to signal is found to be

$$e_{s,n}(t, z) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sqrt{2P_{s,n}(z)} \cos\left[\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_n} t - \beta_s z\right] \quad (4)$$

And the electric field due to crosstalk is expressed as

$$e_{ct,n}(t, z) = \sqrt{2P_{ct}(z)} \cos\left[\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_n} t + \theta_{ct}(t, z)\right] \quad (5)$$

where, $\theta_{ct}(t, z)$ denotes the random phase crosstalk noise.

The local Oscillator has the electric field as

$$e_{LO}(t) = \sqrt{2P_{LO}(t)} \cos\left[\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_n} t\right] \quad (6)$$

The signal power of a WDM system decreases as it travels through the fibre. The signal power at a distance z is [8]

$$P_{s,n}(z) = P_{n0} J_0 e^{-\alpha z} \exp[GJ_0(n-1)Z_e] \left[\sum_{m=1}^N P_{m0} e^{GJ_0(m-1)Z_e} \right]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where,

$$G = \frac{g' \Delta f}{2A}$$

$$Z_e = \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha z}}{\alpha}$$

$$J_0 = \sum_{m=1}^N P_{m0}$$

g' denotes the Raman gain slope, Δf indicates the inter-channel frequency spacing, Z_e is the effective propagation distance and α is the fibre attenuation coefficient.

The signal power can be written as, [8]

$$P_{s,n}(z) = NP_p e^{-\alpha z} \exp\left[\left(\frac{GJ_0 Z_e}{2}\right)(2n - N - 1)\right] \left[\frac{\sinh\left(\frac{GJ_0 Z_e}{2}\right)}{\sinh\left(\frac{NGJ_0 Z_e}{2}\right)} \right] \quad (8)$$

Crosstalk of a system increases as the signals go along the distance. At a distance z the crosstalk power of the WDM system can be expressed by [5]

$$P_{ct}(z) = \left[1 - N \exp\left[-GNP_0 Z_e \frac{(N-1)}{2}\right] \left[\frac{\sinh\left(\frac{NP_0 G Z_e}{2}\right)}{\sinh\left(\frac{N^2 P_0 G Z_e}{2}\right)} \right] P_0 e^{-\alpha z} \right] \quad (9)$$

In case of small crosstalk when $P_0 G Z_e \ll 1$ [8]

$$P_{ct}(z) = \frac{N}{2} (N - 1) P_0 G Z_e \quad (10)$$

We have considered Coherent PSK detection. In case of PSK detection the coupler shifts either of the signal field to 180° . The electric field on the upper and lower photodiodes are [9]

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (E_S + E_{LO}) \quad (11)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (E_S - E_{LO}) \quad (12)$$

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{2P_S} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_S}(t) + \sqrt{2P_{LO}} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_{LO}}(t) \right) \quad (13)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{2P_S} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_S}(t) - \sqrt{2P_{LO}} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_{LO}}(t) \right) \quad (14)$$

The output photocurrents at the receiver end are, [9]

$$I_1(t) = \frac{R}{2} \left[\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{2P_S} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_S}(t) + \sqrt{2P_{LO}} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_{LO}}(t)}{\sqrt{2}} \right\} \right]^{ms} \quad (15)$$

$$I_1(t) = \frac{R}{2} [P_S + P_{LO} + 2\sqrt{P_S P_{LO}} \cos\{\omega_{IF}(t) + \theta_{sig}(t) - \theta_{LO}(t)\}] \quad (16)$$

$$I_2(t) = \frac{R}{2} \left[\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{2P_S} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_S}(t) - \sqrt{2P_{LO}} \cos\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda_{LO}}(t)}{\sqrt{2}} \right\} \right]^{ms} \quad (17)$$

$$I_2(t) = \frac{R}{2} [P_S + P_{LO} - 2\sqrt{P_S P_{LO}} \cos\{\omega_{IF}(t) + \theta_{sig}(t) - \theta_{LO}(t)\}] \quad (18)$$

The summing content of the output current is considered as zero as it will exceed the bandwidth of the photodiode. So, the output current at the receiving end will be,

$$I(t) = 2R\sqrt{P_S(t)P_{LO}} \cos\{\omega_{IF}(t) + \theta_{sig}(t) - \theta_{LO}(t)\} + i_{sh,n} \quad (19)$$

For PSK modulation, the signal power P_S is constant and the signal phase is

$$\theta_{sig}(t) = \theta_s(t) + \theta_{sn}(t)$$

where $\theta_{sn}(t)$ is the phase noise and $\theta_s(t)$ defines the phase modulation. So, [9]

$$I(t) = 2R\sqrt{P_S(t)P_{LO}} \cos\{\omega_{IF}(t) + \theta_s(t) + \theta_{sn}(t) - \theta_{LO}(t)\} + i_{sh,n} \quad (20)$$

Now we can write the receiver output Current as

$$I(t) = 2R\sqrt{P_S(t)P_{LO}} \cos\{\omega_{IF}(t) + \theta_s(t) + \theta_n(t)\} + i_{sh,n} \quad (21)$$

Considering Heterodyne coherent detection, the IF signal Power at the receiver is

$$P_{sig,IF} = 2R^2 P_S P_{LO} \quad (22)$$

Thermal noise of the receiver is

$$\sigma_{th}^2 = \frac{4ktB}{R} \quad (23)$$

The crosstalk variance at the output of receiver is

$$\sigma_{ct}^2 = (RP_{ct})^2 \quad (24)$$

The ASE noise power is[5]

$$P_{ASE} = h\nu\eta B_0 T \left[G_0 - 1 + \frac{G_0\alpha}{GP_0} \left(e^{\alpha z} - \frac{1}{G_0} \right) \right] \quad (25)$$

where, Gain $G_0 = \exp(GZ_e P_0)$, $h\nu = 6.63 \times 10^{-34} J$ is the photon energy, ηT is the thermal equilibrium photon number and B_0 is the optical bandwidth. The ASE noise variance is

$$\sigma_{ASE}^2 = (RP_{ASE})^2 \quad (26)$$

The shot noise at the output of receiver due to signal, Crosstalk and Local Oscillator power is given by,

$$\sigma_{shot}^2 = 2eBR_d(P_s + P_{ct}) \quad (27)$$

The IF signal to crosstalk plus noise ratio is

$$(SCNR)_{IF} = \frac{P_{SIG,IF}}{\sigma_{ct}^2 + \sigma_{ASE}^2 + \sigma_{th}^2 + \sigma_{shot}^2} \quad (28)$$

Bit Error Rate (BER) of the heterodyne phase shift keying (PSK) coherent receiver is

$$BER = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc}(\sqrt{(SCNR)_{IF}}) \quad (29)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analytical approach presented in the previous section has been evaluated at a bit rate of 10 Gbps including all the crosstalk and noise for a phase shift keying modulation. Results are evaluated using MATLAB software.

Table -1 Value Of Parameters Used For Analysis

Parameter	Value
Effective area of core, Aeff	50 μm^2
Raman gain slope, g'	4.9 $\times 10^{-18}$ m/(WGHz)
Channel spacing, Δf	10 ~100 GHz
Fiber attenuation constant, α	0.046km $^{-1}$
Operating wavelength, λ_{eff}	1550nm
Pump power, P0	2 ~ 10 mW
Local Oscillatorpower, PLO	2-30mW
IFBPF Bandwidth, BIF	10GHz

Fig. 2 Plots of ASE noise power versus Distance for different channel spacing at a certain pump power

The plots of Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) noise as a function of distance is shown in Fig. 2 with channel spacing 10 GHz, 12.5 GHz, 15 GHz at a pump power 10 mW. It is noticed that ASE noise power increases significantly with the increase in distance travelled by the signal due to amplified spontaneous emission. The effect of ASE noise is less at a smaller distance as observed that the ASE noise power increases from -150 dB to -136 dB for distance of 50 km. It is further noticed that the ASE noise power can be reduced if channel spacing is increased.

Fig. 3 Plots of IF signal to crosstalk plus noise ratio versus input signal power at a distance 50km

Plots of IF SCNR versus input signal power are shown at Fig.3 for a distance of 50 km and local oscillator power of 15 mW for number of Channel 16, 32 and 64 at pump power 4 mW and 12 mW. The SCNR improves as the signal power increases due to increase in signal strength. If the number of Channel is increased then IF signal to crosstalk plus noise ratio reduces due to higher crosstalk induced by ASE. There is a further reduction of IF SCNR with the increase in pump power at a certain local oscillator power due to high value of induced crosstalk.

Fig. 4 IF SCNR vs Input signal power at different distance for 128channels

Plots of IF signal to crosstalk plus noise ratio versus Input signal power for 128 channels with pump power 8 mW at a distance of 50 km, 80 km, 100 km and 120 km are shown in Fig. 4. It is seen that for a fixed Local Oscillator power 10 mW the IF SCNR decreases as the distance travelled by a signal is increased due to high ASE induced crosstalk.

From the analysis maximum allowable transmission distance can be found for a certain SCNR.

Fig. 5 Plots of power penalty versus number of WDM channel at a SCNR of 40 dB

Plots of power penalty versus number of channel at IF SCNR of 40 dB in a WDM system is shown in Fig. 5. It is seen that the system suffers considerable power penalty due to increase in number of channel. Power penalty become 6 dB if number of channels is increased from 16 to 32. The power penalty increases up to 18 dB with the increase of channels from 16 to 128.

Fig. 6 Plots of BER vs signal power at a distance of 50 km for various parameters

Plots of BER versus signal power at a distance of 50 km for 16, 32 and 64 channels with pump power 4 mw and 12 mw are shown in Fig. 6. The BER performance deteriorates with the increase in number of channel due to induced crosstalk. For example, at a BER of 10⁻¹⁰ the signal power required for 16 channels is -35 dBm but required signal power for 64 channels is -23 dBm. This figure clearly depicts that BER performance is highly affected by increased pump power due to amplifier spontaneous emission.

Fig. 7 Plots of BER vs signal power for 128 channels at a distance of 4 km, 6 km, 8 km and 12 km

Plots of BER vs signal power for 128 channels at a distance of 4 km, 6 km, 8 km, 12 km with local oscillator power 10 mW is shown in Figure 7. It is found that the BER deteriorates with the increase in distance travelled by signal due to amplifier spontaneous emission. The system suffers power penalty at a given BER. The maximum allowable transmission distance at a given BER is also found from the analysis. It is seen that the allowable transmission distance at a BER of 10^{-10} with a signal power -6 dBm is 6 km.

Fig. 8 Plot of power penalty versus distance at a BER of 10^{-10} for a WDM link with N=128

Plots of power penalty vs distance at a BER of 10^{-10} for 128 channels are shown in Fig.8 with local oscillator power of 10 mW. It is seen that the power penalty increases linearly with the increase in distance. It is seen that the power penalty for 5 km is 0.9 dBm and for 10 km is 1.9 dBm.

Fig. 9 Plots of power penalty of a WDM system at a BER of 10^{-10} for 128 channels at different local oscillator power

Plots of power penalty versus distance travelled by a signal in a WDM system of heterodyne coherent receiver at a certain BER of 10^{-10} are shown in Fig. 9. There is an increment of power penalty with the increase in local oscillator power due to amplifier induced crosstalk. For example, at a distance of 12 km the power penalty for local oscillator power 5 mW is 2.2 dBm, 8 mW is 2.35 dBm and 10 mW is 2.5 dBm.

However, in case of OOK modulation the system suffers greater power penalty than PSK modulation and the BER performance is better in PSK modulation [4].

CONCLUSIONS

An analytical approach is presented to evaluate the bit error rate performance of a wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) transmission system with Raman amplifier considering PSK modulation and optical heterodyne receiver. Analysis is done to evaluate the amount of crosstalk due to Raman amplifier induced crosstalk and to get a constant amplitude at receiver. It is found that BER degrades severely with distance due to crosstalk and system suffers considerable power penalty at a given BER and can be minimized by increasing the local oscillator power at the receiving end. The outcome of the analysis is to use PSK modulation instead of ASK modulation to get smooth output at the receiving end. The analysis presented here will find its application considering the limitations of crosstalk in a WDM transmission link.

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